

Studies on Some Thioindigoids: 2-(5-,6- and 7-Nitro)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos and 3-indole-2'-(5',6'- and 7'-Nitro) thionaphthene indigos

S. K. Guha, J. N. Chatterjea and R. S. Gandhi

3-Acetoxy-(5-,6- and 7-nitro)-thionaphthenes were respectively condensed with appropriate acenaphthenequinones and isatins to obtain 2-(5-,6- and 7-nitro)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos and 3-indole-2'-(5',6'- and 7'-nitro)-thionaphtheneindigos. An examination of their colour and absorption maxima values revealed that the colour change of these dyes in both the series runs in the order: 6-nitro > 5-nitro > 7-nitro. The position of the parent compounds with respect to these isomeric nitro dyes has been also worked out. Attempt to synthesise 3-acetoxy-4-nitro-thionaphthene in this connection was not met with success.

In extension of the previous work, reported from this laboratory on the influence of different types of substituents, $-\text{CH}_3$, $-\text{Cl}$, $-\text{OCH}_3$ and $-\text{Br}$ in different positions of the thionaphthene ring of the Ciba Scarlet G and its derivatives, Thioindigo Scarlet R and its derivatives, it was considered interesting and useful to study the effect of the colour producing $-\text{NO}_2$ group in the same manner as previously investigated. Hence, 3-acetoxy-(5-, 6- and 7-nitro)-thionaphthene were made use of for the synthesis of 2-(5-, 6- and 7-nitro)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos (A, B & C) and 3-indole-2'-(5', 6'- and 7'-nitro)-thionaphthene-indigos (D, E & F).

A. 2-(5-Nitro)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos (I, a-d). The thioindigoids were synthesised from 3-acetoxy-5-nitro thionaphthene and acenaphthenequinone, its 3-bromo-, 1-methoxy- and 3:4-dinitro- derivatives respectively. The violet red, deep red and violet crystalline products were produced in 50-75% yield. The dyes (I, a-d) form respectively blue, violet, purple and amethyst solution in conc. H_2SO_4 .

	a	b	c	d
R	H	OCH_3	H	H
R'	H	H	Br	NO_2
R''	H	H	H	NO_2

I, a-d.

B. 2-(6-Nitro)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos (II, a-d). Here the vat dyes were obtained by condensing 3-acetoxy-6-nitro-thionaphthene with the same acenaphthenequinones as used in the 5-nitro series. The new products were red, violet, dark violet and darkish violet needles. Their yields varied between 61-67%. These substances II, a-d,

dissolve in conc. H_2SO_4 producing blue, greenish blue, bluish violet and violet solutions respectively.

II, a-d.

	a	b	c	d
R	H	OCH_3	H	H
R'	H	H	Br	NO_2
R''	H	H	H	NO_2

C. 2-(7-Nitro)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene indigos (III, a-d). The dyes of this 7-nitro series were prepared from 3-acetoxy-7-nitro-thionaphthene and various acenaphthenequinones as used in the two previous series. These are orange, red, dark violet, and light brown needle shaped crystalline substances obtained in 55.5-76 % yield. When treated with conc. H_2SO_4 , the compounds III, a-d, produced violet, bluish violet, purple and amethyst solutions.

III, a-d.

	a	b	c	d
R	H	OCH_3	H	H
R'	H	H	Br	NO_2
R''	H	H	H	NO_2

The different compounds mentioned under A, B and C were all crystallised from nitrobenzene in beautiful needles not melting below 300° . These are moderately soluble in acetic acid, benzene and xylene; soluble in nitrobenzene and insoluble in ethanol. From the characteristic coloured solution of these dyes in conc. H_2SO_4 , the original compounds are precipitated by the addition of water.

The colour of the three isomeric 2-(5-, 6- and 7-nitro)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos, were examined and their absorption maxima values, determined. It was concluded that the change of colour is in the order of decreasing depth of shade: 6-nitro dye > 5-nitro dye > 7-nitro dye. The parent dye occupies its position, just next to its 5-nitro derivatives, (Table I).

It was also interesting to find that the effect of substitution by $-NO_2$ group in both 5-, and 6- position of the thionaphthene ring of 2-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos (Ciba Scarlet G and its derivatives) causes a bathochromic effect. Moreover, the maximum bathochromic effect was produced in 6-position instead of 5-position, opposite to what was observed in case of substitution by $-CH_3$, $-Cl$, $-OCH_3$ and Br atom. This result also indicated that Martinet's rule² is not applicable to 2-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos as far as one nitro group in the thionaphthene part of the dye molecule is concerned

(cf. 5- and 6-mononitro thioindigos, where 6-nitro product was found deeper than the 5-nitro dye³). Similarly the symmetrical dye, 5:5'-dinitrothioindigo was found orange and the 6:6'-dinitro dye, violet.

TABLE I

Compounds	$\lambda_{\text{Xylene max}}$
2-(6-Nitro)-thionaphthene-AI (IIa)	499 m μ
2-(5-Nitro)-thionaphthene-AI (Ia)	481
2-(7-Nitro)-thionaphthene-AI (IIIa)	472
2-Thionaphthene-AI (Ciba Scarlet G)	477.5*
2-(6-Nitro)-thionaphthene-8'-(1'-methoxy)AI (IIb)	545
2-(5-Nitro)-thionaphthene-8'-(1'-methoxy)-AI (Ib)	530
2-(7-Nitro)-thionaphthene-8'-(1'-methoxy)-AI (IIIb)	483
2-Thionaphthene-8'-(1'-methoxy)-AI (Methoxy Ciba Scarlet G)	524*
2-(6-Nitro)-thionaphthene-8'-(3'-bromo) AI (IIC)	537
2-(5-Nitro)-thionaphthene-8'-(3'-bromo)-AI (IC)	521
2-(7-Nitro)-thionaphthene-8'-(3'-bromo)-AI (IIIC)	478
2-Thionaphthene-8'-(3'-bromo)-AI (Ciba Red R)	518*
2-(6-Nitro)-thionaphthene-8'-(3':4'-dinitro)-AI (IIId)	534.5
2-(5-Nitro)-thionaphthene-8'-(3':4'-dinitro)-AI (Id)	515
2-(7-Nitro)-thionaphthene-8'-(3':4'-dinitro)-AI (IIId)	508
2-Thionaphthene-8'-(3':4'-dinitro)-AI.	514

In Table I & III, AI denotes acenaphthylene-indigo.

D. 3-Indole-2'-(5'-nitro)-thionaphthene-indigos (IV, a-e). These thioindigoids of this class were prepared by condensing isatin, its 5-chloro-, 5-bromo-, 5-nitro- and 5:7-dinitro-derivatives with 3-acetoxy-5-nitro-thionaphthene respectively. The new compounds are violet, brownish violet, dark red and red needles, produced in 61-71% yield. The substances, IV, a-e, develop respectively blood red, purple, violet (both from o and e) and red colouration with Conc. H₂SO₄.

	a	b	c	d	e
R	H	NO ₂	NO ₂	Cl	Br
R'	H	H	NO ₂	H	H

3. N. S. Dokunikhin and Yu. E. Gerasimenko, *Zhur. Obshchei Khim.*, 1960, **30**, 635, 1231.

4. S. K. Guha, *This Journal*, 1932, **9**, 423.

*Idem, *This Journal*, 1944, **21**, 91; S. K. Guha, J. N. Chatterjea and A. K. Mitra, *Chem. Ber.*, 1961, **94**, 3297.

E. 3-Indole-2'-(6'-nitro)-thionaphthene-indigos (V, a-e). These dyes resulted from the condensation of 3-acetoxy-6-nitro-thionaphthene with the same isatins as used in the 5-nitro series. The products are dark violet and violet needles which are perceptibly deeper than the corresponding 5-nitro dyes. Their yield varied between 56.2-76.6%. The compounds, V a-e, dissolve in conc. H_2SO_4 producing amethyst, purple (both from b & d), deep violet and violet solutions respectively.

V, a-e.

	a	b	c	d	e
R	H	NO ₂	NO ₂	Cl	Br
R'	H	H	NO ₂	H	H

F. 3-Indole-2'-(7'-nitro)-thionaphthene-indigos (VI, a-e). The compounds of this 7'-nitro series were synthesised from 3-acetoxy-7-nitrothionaphthene and similar isatins utilised under D & E. The dyes are brownish violet, violet, orange red and orange crystalline substances obtained in 60-71% yield. These indigos (VI, a-e) form respectively blood red, purple (both from b & c), red and rosy red solutions in conc. H_2SO_4 .

VI, a-e.

	a	b	c	d	e
R	H	NO ₂	NO ₂	Cl	Br
R'	H	H	NO ₂	H	H

All the isomeric indole-indigos of 5', 6'- and 7'-nitro series were also crystallised from nitrobenzene in fine needles melting above 300° and their solubility is similar to those mentioned with regard to the 5-, 6- and 7-nitro-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene indigos (loc. cit.).

A comparative study of colour and absorption maxima values of the isomeric 3-indole-2'-(5', 6'- and 7'-nitro)-thionaphthene-indigos, recorded in the table II and IV, indicated clearly that the general order of colour change is the same as those of 2-(5-, 6- and 7-nitro)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos (table I) but here the position of the parent dye is next to the 7-nitro compound with the exception of the irregular position of 3-(5-chloro-, 5-bromo-) indole-2'-thionaphthene-indigos which take their position next to the 6'-nitro derivative. Further, it was also observed in this isatin series that 6'-nitro dyes are deeper in colour than the 5'-nitro dyes and thus invalidating Martinet's rule as far as one $-NO_2$ group is concerned.

TABLE II

Compounds		λ_{max} Xylene m μ
3-Indole-2'-(6'-nitro)-TI	(Va)	529
3-Indole-2'-(5'-nitro)-TI	(IVa)	501
3-Indole-2'-(7'-nitro)-TI	(VIa)	494
3-Indole-2'-TI (Thioindigo Scarlet R).		489.2***
3-(5-Nitro)indole-2'-(6'-nitro)-TI	(Vb)	544
3-(5-Nitro)indole-2'-(5'-nitro)-TI	(IVb)	532
3-(5-Nitro) indole-2'-(7'-nitro)-TI	(VIb)	498
3-(5-Nitro)indole-2'-TI		417
3-(5:7-Dinitro) indole-2'-(6'-nitro)-TI	(Vc)	540
3-(5:7-Dinitro) indole-2'-(5'-nitro)-TI	(IVc)	492
3-(5:7-Dinitro) indole-2'-(7'-nitro)-TI	(VIc)	490
3-(5:7-Dinitro)indole-2'-TI		438****
3-(5-Chloro)indole-2'-(6'-nitro)-TI	(Vd)	522
3-(5-Chloro)indole-2'-(5'-nitro)-TI	(IVd)	494
3-(5-Chloro)indole-2'-(7'-nitro)-TI	(VI d)	491
3-(5-Chloro)indole-2'-TI		512
3-(5-Bromo)indole-2'-(6'-nitro)-TI	(Ve)	526
3-(5-Bromo)indole-2'-(5'-nitro)-TI	(IVe)	506
3-(5-Bromo)indole-2'-(7'-nitro)-TI	(VIe)	499
3-(5-Bromo)indole-2'-TI.		516

In table II & IV, TI denotes thionaphthenc-indigo.

EXPERIMENTAL

The 2-(5-, 6- and 7-nitro)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos mentioned in table III were prepared by heating the glacial acetic acid about (3-6 ml.) the constituents in presence of 2 drops of strong hydrochloric acid for 15 min. to 1 hr., collected and crystallised.

In table IV, 3-indole-2'-(5'-, 6'- and 7'-nitro)-thionaphthene-indigos are described. These dyes were similarly obtained from the reactants by heating for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. in glacial acetic acid (3-5 ml.) solution, and crystallised similarly. On account of the difficulty in synthesising the requisite intermediates in quantity, the nitro dyes could not be prepared in sufficient amount for developing shade on cotton.

The 3-(5-chloro-, 5-bromo- and 5-nitro-) indole-2'-thionaphthene-indigos required now for comparison of colour in this investigation were prepared in the usual way from the constituents in 10 ml. glacial acetic acid and heating for 30 min. in presence of 3 drops of strong hydrochloric acid and crystallised from glacial acetic acid melting above 300°. These are soluble in xylene; moderately soluble in nitrobenzene and acetic acid, slightly soluble in benzene and insoluble in ethanol and carbon tetrachloride. There dyed shade developed uniformly on cotton at 65° from an yellow alkaline hydrosulphite vat.

*** S. K. Guha, *This Journal*, 1939, **16**, 219.

**** S. K. Guha, J. N. Chatterjea and A. K. Mitra, *Chem. Ber.*, 1961, **94**, 2295.

TABLE III

2-(5-, 6- and 7-nitro)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos

Serial No.	Dyes	Colour and appearance.	Yield in %	Action of Conc. H ₂ SO ₄ .	Molecular formula	Analysis of Nitrogen %	
						Found;	Req.
Ia	2-(5-Nitro)-T-AI.	Violet-red shining needles	65	Blue.	C ₂₀ H ₉ NO ₄ S.	3.78;	3.89.
Ib	2-(5-Nitro)-T-8'-(1'-methoxy)-AI.	Shining violet needles.	50	Purple.	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ NO ₅ S.	3.43;	3.59
Ic	2-(5-Nitro)-T-8'-(3'-bromo)-AI.	Deep red needles.	75	Violet.	C ₂₀ H ₈ NBrO ₄ S.	2.42;	3.19
Id	2-(5-Nitro)-T-8'-(3'-4'-dinitro)-AI	Darkish violet red needles.	61	Amethyst.	C ₂₀ H ₇ N ₃ O ₈ S.	9.55;	9.35.
IIa	2-(6-Nitro)-T-AI.	Coppery lusture red needles.	66.5	Blue.	C ₂₀ H ₉ NO ₄ S	4.12;	3.89
IIb	2-(6-Nitro)-T-8'-(1'-methoxy)-AI	Dark violet shining needles.	64.5	Bluish violet	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ NO ₅ S	3.62;	3.59.
IIc	2-(6-Nitro)-T-8'-(3'-bromo)-AI	Violet silky needles.	67.5	Greenish blue	C ₂₀ H ₈ NBrO ₄ S	3.31;	3.19.
IId	2-(6-Nitro)-T-8'-(3'-4'-dinitro)-AI	Darkish violet needles.	61	Violet	C ₂₀ H ₇ N ₃ O ₈ S	9.12;	9.35.
IIIa	2-(7-Nitro)-T-AI	Silky orange needles.	76.6	Violet.	C ₂₀ H ₉ NO ₄ S.	3.95;	3.89.
IIIb	2-(7-Nitro)-T-8'-(1'-methoxy)-AI	Dark violet shining needles.	70.6	Purple.	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ NO ₅ S.	3.35;	3.59.
IIIc	2-(7-Nitro)-T-8'-(3'-bromo)AI	Red needles.	58.1	Bluish violet	C ₂₀ H ₈ NBrO ₄ S	3.65;	3.19.
IIId	2-(7-Nitro)-T-8'-(3';4'-dinitro)-AI	Light brown needles.	55.5	Amethyst.	C ₂₀ H ₇ N ₃ O ₈ S.	9.48	9.35

TABLE IV

3-Indole-2'-(5', 6'- and 7'-nitro)-thionaphthene-indigos

Serial No.	Dyes	Colour and appearance.	Yield in %	Action of Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Molecular formula	Analysis of Nitrogen %	
						Found	Req.
IVa	3-Indole-2'-(5'-nitro)-TI	Shining violet needles	61	Blood red.	C ₁₆ H ₈ N ₂ O ₄ S.	8.71	8.64
IVb	3-(5-Chloro)indole-2'-(5'-nitro)-TI	Brownish violet needles	71	Purple.	C ₁₆ H ₇ N ₂ ClO ₄ S.	7.79	7.81
IVc	3-(5-Bromo)indole-2'-(5'-nitro)-TI	Dark brownish violet	69	Violet.	C ₁₆ H ₇ N ₂ BrO ₄ S.	6.99	6.94
IVd	3-(5-Nitro)indole-2'-(5'-nitro)-TI	Shining red needles	70	Red.	C ₁₆ H ₇ N ₃ O ₆ S.	11.10	11.38
IVe	3-(5-7-Dinitro)indole-2'-(5'-nitro)TI	Darkish red needles	63	Violet.	C ₁₆ H ₆ N ₄ O ₈ S.	13.80	13.52
Va	3-Indole-2'-(6'-nitro)-TI.	Dark violet needles	60	Amethyst.	C ₁₆ H ₈ N ₂ O ₄ S.	8.99	8.64
Vb	3-(5-Chloro)indole-2'-(6'-nitro)-TI	Do., deeper than Va.	59.1	Purple.	C ₁₆ H ₇ N ₂ ClO ₄ S	7.76	7.81

TABLE IV (Cont.)

Serial No.	Dyes	Colour and appearance.	Yield in %	Action of Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Molecular formula	Analysis of Nitrogen %	
						Found	Req.
Vc	3-(5-Bromo)indole-2'-(6'-nitro)-TI	Do., deeper than Vb	56.2	Deep violet	C ₁₆ H ₇ N ₂ BrO ₄ S	6.88	6.94
Vd	3-(5-Nitro) indole-2'-(6'-nitro) TI	Violet red needles	65	Purple.	C ₁₆ H ₇ N ₃ O ₆ S.	11.20	11.38
Ve	3-(5-7-Dinitro)indole-2'-(6'-nitro)TI	Dark violet glistening needles	76.6	Violet.	C ₁₆ H ₆ N ₄ O ₈ S.	13.90	13.52
VIa	3-Indole-2'-(7'-nitro)-TI	Brown needles.	60	Blood red.	C ₁₆ H ₈ N ₂ O ₄ S.	8.59	8.64
VIb	3-(5-Chloro)indole-2'-(7'-nitro)-TI	Darkish violet needles	71	Purple.	C ₁₆ H ₇ N ₂ O ₄ ClS	7.80	7.81
VIc	3-(5-Bromo)indole-2'-(7'-nitro)-TI	Shining violet needles	69	Purple.	C ₁₆ H ₇ N ₂ BrO ₄ S	6.93	6.94
VId	3-(5-Nitro)indole-2'-(7'-nitro)-TI.	Vermillion-red needles	67.6	Red.	C ₁₆ H ₇ N ₃ O ₆ S.	11.30	11.38
VIe	3-(5-7-Dinitro)indole-2'-(7'-nitro)-TI	Scarlet red	63	Rosy-red.	C ₁₆ H ₆ N ₄ O ₈ S.	13.48	13.52

3-(5-Chloro)indole-2'-thionaphthene-indigo: From 5-chloroisatin (0.54 gm.) and 3-hydroxy-thionaphthene (0.45 gm.); yield 0.85 gm. (90.38%) violet-red shining needles; strong H₂SO₄ dissolves it producing a dark greenish black solution. It dyes cotton in darkish red shade (Found: N, 4.84. C₁₆H₈O₂ NClS requires N, 4.46%).

3-(5-Bromo) indole-2'-thionaphthene-indigo: From 5-bromoisatin (0.67 gm.) and 3-hydroxy-thionaphthene (0.45 gm); yield 0.9 gm. (83.5%); deep violet-red shining needles. The colour of the solution of the dye in strong H₂SO₄ resembles that of the foregoing compound, cotton is dyed in violet-red shade. (Found: N, 4.23. calculated for C₁₆H₈O₂ NBrS; N, 3.91%).

3-(5-Nitro) indole-2'-thionaphthene-indigo: From 5-nitroisatin (0.57 gm) and 3-hydroxy-thionaphthene (0.45 gm); yield 0.85 gm. (87.4%); shining darkish violet red needles. It dissolves in strong H₂SO₄ producing a darkish green solution. It dyes cotton in violet shade. (Found: N, 9.03. C₁₆H₈O₄N₂S requires N, 8.64%).

Experiments on the synthesis of 3-acetoxy-4-nitro-thionaphthene have not met with success. 2-chloro⁵ and 2-bromo-6-nitrobenzoic acid⁶ were both recovered unchanged on attempted condensation with thioglycollic acid in alcoholic sodium ethoxide. Attempt to convert 6-nitroanthranilic acid⁷ into 5-nitro-6-carboxylic-phenylthioglycollic acid

5. S. K. Guha, J. N. Chatterjea, A. K. Sinha, *This Journal*, 1955, **32**, 777.

6. J. L. E. Erickson, J. M. Dechary and T. R. Pollig, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 5621.

7. (a) R. Kahn, *Ber.*, 1902, **47**, 471, 3857.

(b) M. T. Bogerot and V. J. Chambers, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, **27**, 651.

following conventional procedure diazotisation, xanthogenation, hydrolysis and condensation with chloroacetic acid have again proved abortive. Therefore a complete picture of thioindigoids with nitro group in all possible positions of the benzene ring of the thionaphthene could not be obtained.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
PATNA UNIVERSITY,
PATNA-5.

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